

Deliverable n. D7.4.

Handbook of protocols and methodology of good agricultural practices in arid and semiarid conditions

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D7.4: Handbook of protocols and methodology of good agricultural practices in arid and semiarid conditions – this handbook will collect all the protocols used or to be used in the various WPs for the harmonization of the procedures and discussion of results (jointly with WP8) (M21)

A Handbook of protocols and methodology of good agricultural practices in arid and semiarid conditions was prepared by Sonia Labidi leader of the WP3 in ProSmallAgriMed project. The handbook will be attached in pdf in English, Francis and Arabic languages. **(Attached file D.7.4)**

Technical guide of the good practices for the cultivation of spineless prickly pear covers in details various topics related to the cultivation of prickly pears such as cultivation conditions, orchards establishment, irrigation, fertilization, pruning and plant protection strategies.

This technical guide is organized in the following paragraphs:

- 1.0 OPTIMAL CULTIVATION CONDITIONS
- 2.0 ORCHARDS ESTABLISHMENT
- 2.1 IRRIGATION
- 2.2 FERTILIZATION
- 2.2.1 CHEMICAL FERTILIZATION
- 2.2.2 ORGANIC FERTILIZATION
- 2.3 PRUNING: SHAPING PRUNING AND FRUITING PRUNING
- 2.4 PLANT PROTECTION

The above paragraphs discuss in detail the experimental protocols used for the various agronomic practices necessary to obtain a good yield and quality of prickly pear.

Furthermore, protocols and methodology of good agricultural practices in arid and semiarid conditions were collected in the MOOC too, in the Session I and II. **Lesson 1, 2, 3 and 4** included in **session I** are available at the link: <https://sites.google.com/view/prosmallagrinedproject/home-page/crop-management> (**Attached file D.7.1**)

- **Session I - Crop management**
- Lesson 1 - Agro-Ecosystem functioning in drylands, with special emphasis to cactus pear (Saia/Terracciano/Angeletti)
- Lesson 2 - Crop management under arid areas to increase the potential, attainable and actual yields (Liguori/Labidi)
- Lesson 3 - Intercropping of perennials with annual crops (Angeletti/Terracciano/Saia)
- Lesson 4 - Other agronomic aspects (Terracciano/Angeletti/Saia/Righetti)

Lesson 5 and 6 included in **session II** are available at the link:

<https://sites.google.com/view/prosmallagrinedproject/home-page/soil-management>

Session II - Soil management

Lesson 5 - Soil management under arid areas to increase water availability (Angeletti/Terracciano/Saia)

Lesson 6 - Soil inoculation with symbiotic microbes (Lingua/Massa/Campana)

